

This document details the contents of the experimental data and analysis scripts files published to accompany Bliss et al. 2023, Biology Letters "A spontaneous gravity prior: Newborn chicks prefer stimuli that move against gravity".

Experiment 1 - DLC output files.zip

Zip file containing the results of tracking in Experiment 1. Each csv file contains the tracking results for a subject, as generated by DeepLabCut.

Experiment 1 – metadata.xlsx

Excel file containing the metadata about subjects of Experiment 1. For each subject, it gives the ID and the sex of the chick, the ID of the arena where the experiment took place, the location of the downward stimulus ('stimulus_location'), the frame number of the video where the experiment started (i.e., where the chick was placed in the arena; 'startframes') and where it ended (i.e. when 20 minutes have passed; 'endframes').

Experiment 1 – python output files.zip

Zip file containing the subjects' position in the arena in Experiment 1. Each csv file contains the observed positions of one subject, as generated by the Python script 'Gravity Script Final'.

Experiment 1 - results.csv

Csv file containing the summary of the results for Experiment 1. For each chick ('ID'), the file contains its sex, the preference indices at the four time bins ('t1', 't2', 't3', 't4'), the first choice ('first_approach') and the approach latency ('latency').

Experiment 2 - DLC output files.zip

Zip file containing the results of tracking in Experiment 2. Each csv file contains the tracking results for a subject, as generated by DeepLabCut.

Experiment 2 – metadata.xlsx

Excel file containing the metadata about subjects of Experiment 2. For each subject, it gives the ID and the sex of the chick, the ID of the arena where the experiment took place, the location of the downward stimulus ('stimulus_location'), the frame number of the video where the experiment started (i.e., where the chick was placed in the arena; 'startframes') and where it ended (i.e. when 20 minutes have passed; 'endframes').

Experiment 2 – python output files.zip

Zip file containing the subjects' position in the arena in Experiment 2. Each csv file contains the observed positions of one subject, as generated by the Python script 'Gravity Script Final'.

Experiment 2 - results.csv

Csv file containing the summary of the results for Experiment 2. For each chick ('ID'), the file contains its sex, the preference indices at the four time bins ('t1', 't2', 't3', 't4'), the first choice ('first_approach') and the approach latency ('latency').

Experiment 3 – DLC output files.zip

Zip file containing the results of tracking in Experiment 3. Each csv file contains the tracking results for a subject, as generated by DeepLabCut.

Experiment 3 – metadata.xlsx

Excel file containing the metadata about subjects of Experiment 3. For each subject, it gives the ID and the sex of the chick, the ID of the arena where the experiment took place, the location of the accelerating stimulus ('stimulus_location'), the frame number of the video where the experiment started (i.e., where the chick was placed in the arena; 'startframes') and where it ended (i.e. when 20 minutes have passed; 'endframes').

Experiment 3 - python output files.zip

Zip file containing the subjects' position in the arena in Experiment 3. Each csv file contains the observed positions of one subject, as generated by the Python script 'Gravity Script Final'.

Experiment 3 - results.csv

Csv file containing the summary of the results for Experiment 3. For each chick ('ID'), the file contains its sex, the preference indices at the four time bins ('t1', 't2', 't3', 't4'), the first choice ('first_approach') and the approach latency ('latency').

Experiment 4 - DLC output files.zip

Zip file containing the results of tracking in Experiment 4. Each csv file contains the tracking results for a subject, as generated by DeepLabCut.

Experiment 4 – metadata.xlsx

Excel file containing the metadata about subjects of Experiment 1. For each subject, it gives the ID and the sex of the chick, the ID of the arena where the experiment took place, the location of the downward stimulus ('stimulus_location'), the frame number of the video where the experiment started (i.e., where the chick was placed in the arena; 'startframes') and where it ended (i.e. when 20 minutes have passed; 'endframes').

Experiment 4 - python output files.zip

Zip file containing the subjects' position in the arena in Experiment 4. Each csv file contains the observed positions of one subject, as generated by the Python script 'Gravity Script Final'.

Experiment 4 - results.csv

Csv file containing the summary of the results for Experiment 4. For each chick ('ID'), the file contains its sex, the preference indices at the four time bins ('t1', 't2', 't3', 't4'), the first choice ('first_approach') and the approach latency ('latency').

python script - DLC Evaluation Final.txt

Python code that evaluates the quality of tracking. The script takes the DLC output files as input and returns the subject IDs of the accepted and non-accepted (low quality) tracks.

python script - Gravity Script Final.txt

Python code that evaluates the subjects' position in the arena. The script takes the DLC output files as input and saves the frame-by-frame position (left, centre or right) of the chick.

python script - Latency of First Move Final.txt

Python code that calculates the latency of the first choice. The script takes the csv files generated with Gravity Script Final.py as input and returns the time elapsed until the first choice.

python script - Preference Analysis Final.txt

Python code that calculates the preference index. The script takes the csv files generated with Gravity Script Final.py as input and returns the preference indices.